

The Refusal Catcalling Strategy by Women in Makassar: Semiotics Analysis

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ABSTRACT: The research analyzed the refusal catcalling strategy by women in Makassar. Furthermore, with the catcalling topic still being addressed by Makassar residents, this research delves deeper into the link between signs and the refusal strategy of catcalling on women in Makassar and those who regard it as harassing conduct. The research aims to explore strategies used by females in dealing with the refusal sign of catcalling in Makassar. In addition, the research examines Ferdinand Saussure's theory in analyzing sign such as signifier and signified theory in arranging refusal strategy of catcalling. The results of the research is the women must have strategies to overcome the refusal of catcalling such as ignoring to the perpetrator, fighting to the perpetrator, reporting to the police, leave, places prone to catcalling, pretending to call family, and reprimanding with sound loudly.

KEYWORDS: Catcalling; Makassar, the refusal strategy; Semiotics; Women.

INTRODUCTION

Humans communicate with other interlocutors regarding signs in order to grasp what is being sent by speaker. As line with Mehawesh, (2014) refers people can communicate with the use of signs. To avoid misunderstanding, people must equate concepts to grasp these indications. Abakumova et al., (2022) stated that signs include verbal and non-verbal aspects. The verbal sign includes speech, language, and sound, whereas the nonverbal sign includes gestures, actions, and strategies; both become signs when given meaning. Somadi et al., (2022) declared semiotics studies the process of signing something, both physical and mental, and then giving meaning. People may learn from semiotics science that the world is filled with signs that anything can understand it (Rahman & Weda, 2019; Sukmawaty et al., 2022).

Furthermore, if signs can be deciphered, individuals can communicate to comprehend the provided sign-in language. As a result, they can adapt to their surroundings. In brief, people can grasp the message provided through communication, although signs are not always fully understood and comparable by others. Each individual has their explanation with various background experiences (Murphy, 1998; Little, 2002; Gutiérrez, 2003; Wei, 2011).

Unlike the experts mentioned above, the research demonstrated the relationship between signs and experience using semiotics analysis. Certain semiotics writers have proposed Semiotics. Lestel, (2006) suggests without semiotics, it will never find signs that occur in social environments. Individuals interpret events in their lives differently than others. Because everyone has distinct experiences, there is a difference in meaning. Not only knowledge and affection occur when the occurrence is experienced in this life. It is also tied to each human's memory, ideas, and other qualities before sustaining it. Besides that, Metro-Roland, (2009) concludes that such an effect is the end of the semiotic process. However, it does not imply that all signs are mind; Pierce stresses essential facts in his sign theory, demonstrating that sure signs are experiences (Andini et al., 2022; Asha et al., 2022).

Regarding examples of catcalling encounters by Indonesian men towards women, in the first case, the person is an Indonesian man who believes he has grasped a woman's breast without marriage. It is known as catcalling, and it is pretty standard in Indonesia. When a citizen views anything cognitively, two processes occur in their mind: clutching the chest is a Signifier, and the way thought is as Signified. Meanwhile, the second case is an American citizen with a different experience and cognition from the first. Touching the chest of the opposite sex without regard for marital status is customary in their nation; thus, they tend to relax when they see a female being stroked. In line with Bretthauer et al., (2007) considered female objectification will show that males have power. Therefore, if the communicator feels uncomfortable with the surrounding, it can be categorized as catcalling (Walton & Pedersen, 2021).

Based on the statement above, this also happened in Makassar; catcalling can be felt by almost every public place user, such as roads, public transportation, work area and even campus area. As for some evidence of catcalling or harassment that occurred in Makassar such as first, dosen UNM diduga melecehkan mahasiswa saat bimbingan (UNM lecturer allegedly harassed student) during guidance published in detiksulsel newspaper on Friday, July 08, 2022 at 23.46. <https://www.detik.com/sulsel/hukum-dan-2941>

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kriminal/d-6170016/oknum-dosen-unm-diduga-lecehkan-mahasiswa-saat-bimbingan-dinonaktifkan. Second, mahasiswa Unhas Mengalami Pelecehan Seksual (Unhas Students Experience Sexual Harassment) was published in the Hasanuddin University Identity newspaper on Tuesday, May 14, 2022. <https://identitasunhas.com/lagi-mahasiswa-unhas-alami-pelecehan-seksual/>. Third, korban Pelecehan di UIN Alauddin Enggan Laporkan ke Polisi Dinilai Wajar, Sosiolog Jelaskan Alasannya (Victim of Harassment at UIN Alauddin Reluctants to Report to the Police Judged Reasonable, Sociologist Explains it) the Reason published in Fajar.co.id newspaper on Wednesday, March 22, 2022 <https://fajar.co.id/2023/03/22/korban-pelecehan-di-uin-alauddin-enggan-melapor-ke-polisi-dinilai-wajar-sosiolog-jelaskan-alasannya/>.

Finally, given the continued discussion of the catcalling situation in Makassar, this research investigates the link between signs in semiotics science and the refusal strategy of catcalling in Makassar, as catcalling is regarded as disrespectful by Makassar citizens.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Semiotics

Semiotics is an analytical approach to determining the meaning of a sign. It is assumed in semiotics that social occurrences in society and culture are signs (Wicaksono et al., 2021). According to Trevarthen, (1990), judging a symbol or sign is important; animal life is conveyed through feelings (feeling), but human feelings are conveyed through various concepts, symbols, and language. It investigates the structures, norms, and conventions that enable signs to be meaningful. The study of semiotics occurs in two paradigms, namely the constructive paradigm and the critical paradigm (Ahlqvist & Rhisiart, 2015). The constructivist paradigm is the opposite of an understanding that utilizes observation and objectivity to discover the reality. This paradigm sees social science as a systematic investigation of socially significant activity based on direct and extensive observation of the social actors who shape their social surroundings. The critical paradigm is an alternative paradigm relating to society, intending to criticize and justify the status quo and provide alternative information to establish a better social order (Anriadi et al., 2021).

Etymologically, semiotics comes from the Greek word Simeon which means "sign." Terminologically, semiotics can be defined as a science that studies a wide range of objects. Events of all cultures as signs (Chandler, 2007). de Souza et al., (2010) claims semiotics is a systematic study of the creation and interpretation of signs, how the system works, and what advantages it has on human life. Lyons, (1981) asserted that semiotics is a science that studies signs in their broad meaning in society, both literal and figurative, as well as those using language and non-language. The language, a symbol system, usually contains mysterious things. Behavioral semiotics is creating a particular action or behavior to achieve a specific goal and applying syntactic, semantic, and pragmatic dimensions for analyzing a text (Stamper et al., 2000; Barricelli et al., 2016; Mikhaeil & Baskerville 2019; Lestari et al., 2020). Therefore, it is critical to comprehend signs because semiotics aim to comprehend a sign's meaning so that someone may transmit a speaker to an interlocutor.

B. The Concept of Semiotics Theory by Ferdinand Saussure

Signs explain social processes that develop in a setting, meaning that signs and language are inextricably linked. The first further discussion is significant and signified as it is recognized that significance is the thing that our mind can receive, such as the object's original visual image. Signified is the meaning thought upon receiving the sign. For example, people use the door as an object to explain it as significant and signified. Therefore, the meaning of the door is the part of the word, such as D-O-O-R. While signified from the meaning of the door is what is captured in people's minds when they see the door, which is a tool used to connect one space to another. Language is a text that must be related to the real world or what is really happening in the society (Honig, 1997; Leung, 2005; Sahib et al., 2017). The second discussion is a language subcategory subdivided into language and parole. Hu, (2002) suggested language is people's knowledge about a particular subject. Language can be interpreted as a sign system. At the same time, parole is an act performed individually from the intelligence of an idea. The third concept is synchronic and diachronic, Syntagmatic is the relationship that exists between concrete language units, while paradigmatic means the relationship that is not concrete (relationship in absentia) within language units.

Hence, Ferdinand Saussure's semiotics concept prioritizes signs with verbal communication. Verbal communication is one of the types of communication in which message or information is conveyed to someone orally or in writing. People can exchange thoughts and feelings, convey emotions, feelings, information and ideas through the words they express (van Kleef et al., 2010). In relation to verbal communication with a catcalling sign is an utterance in the form of praise or things that offend the interlocutor in

the form of harassment so that the communication is catcalling. for example Hi, my idol, are you all right?, how are you great woman, and the last is always be happy, Miss Sweet. The underscore utterance is a catcalling expression sign and if interlocutor likes those expression and feel undisturbed so then it is not called a catcalling expression.

C. Catcalling Phenomenon

The term catcalling comes from an animated series created by Tex Avery in 1937. Avery created the popular cartoon wolf character “Little Red Walking Hood”. In the cartoon, the wolf whistles to get the attention of his flock. Therefore, catcalling is considered correct term to describe men's lust for women.

In the Oxford dictionary, catcalling is translated as whistle, shout and comments of a sexual nature. Quinn, (2002) claimed catcalling behavior comments on a female's appearance.

According to Rosenbaum, et al., (2020), catcalling is the use of offensive language, verbal and non-verbal expressions found in public places such as sidewalks and bus stops. Verbal expression aims to include comments about females' object and nonverbal expression also often takes looking and include meaningful physical gesture to assess a female's physical appearance. Apart from that, an abuser will boo or make a fuss of someone in public that makes them uncomfortable.

In Makassar, South Sulawesi, usually this catcalling is in idle compliments form speaks Hi my heart, look here maybe you are my match (Hai pujaan hatiku lihat kesini dong siapa tau kita jodoh). Absurd greeting: You are alone, do you want to be accompanied or not? (Sendirian aja nih, mau ditemani nggak?). And unreasonable attention form: why is your face sullen? You have been dumped with your boyfriend (Kok cemberut? Sudah diputusin sama pacarnya yach....). The facts on the ground show that males vent their attraction to females in order to get attention from them. Even females wear hijab that often hailed on the street. Catcalling victims feel uncomfortable, causing fear to pass through the area. If victims (females) feel offended by the catcalling, they unconsciously judge themselves. catcalling can cause the victim to be like judged objects (self-objectification) (Calogero, 2013).

Actually, women also have the same rights as men to realize of expression freedom in everyday life. It is very inappropriate to associate catcalling events with blaming women's facial expressions and body movements because they want to express themselves and move in some way, women are still vulnerable to catcalling from those around them. As said by Bourne, (2017), women have freedom of expression. Whatever the perpetrators' inspiration on the victim, catcalling act must still be minimized so that women can have a security sense in showing their expression freedom and also not become vulnerable to other street harassment.

D. Refusal Catcalling Strategy

According to O'Leary, (2016), Women use various strategies in dealing with catcalling. This strategy involves neglect to avoid catcalling:

Verbal response: verbal response is a firm response to catcalling perpetrators so that men will not disturb them again. Verbal response marked like “I don't like that”. “Go out” and shout.

Ignoring the behavior: Another strategy many of the participants discussed was ignoring catcalls.

Avoidance: Several participants felt the need to avoid catcallers altogether. This often took the form of taking a different route, crossing the street, avoiding eye contact, or walking with another person in hopes that a catcaller would refrain from engaging in catcalling behavior. Thus, the most important preventing catcalling is the victim's denial and unwillingness to all forms of sexual attention.

METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This research use descriptive qualitative type. This qualitative research begins with assumptions, a worldview, the possible use of a theoretical lens, and research problems that ask about the meaning that individuals or groups attach to a social or human problem. Therefore, this qualitative research design is very supportive because it explains catcalling phenomenon signs to find out strategies for dealing with catcalling in Makassar.

B. Research Participants

Based on previous observations, the participants of this research are women and men who have experienced catcalling. In the sense that women are victims and men are perpetrators of catcalling in Makassar. And also the number of research participants

is thirty-seven people with details of twenty-seven women with different university origins in Makassar.

However, researcher gets information from social media status on the Whatsapp application from relatives so that researcher finds victims and perpetrators of catcalling in Makassar.

C. The Time and Location of the Research

This Research carried out during December 2022-January 2023. It is conducted in seven universities in Makassar. They are Hasanuddin University, State University of Makassar, Islamic University of Makassar, Indonesian Muslim University, STIE Indonesia Makassar, Islamic State University of Makassar, and Bosowa University.

D. Research Instruments

The researcher employs numerous devices to collect data on women's refusal of catcalling strategies in Makassar. First, the researcher observed and took field notes to learn about the catcalling phenomena encountered by women in Makassar. Field notes establish the catcalling methods that women employ when encountering catcalling. Second, the interview is used to identify women's reactions to catcalling based on previous experiences. Additionally, the recording is utilized to document the data collected to enhance and confirm the accuracy of the data acquired.

E. Data Analysis

Data analysis in this research is carried out before and after the completion of the field research. The beginning of data analysis is when the researcher formulates and explains a problem before going directly to the field and continue until the writing of the research results is complete. Furthermore, data analysis is focused and carried out simultaneously with data collection.

The data analysis technique in this research is qualitative data analysis. The researcher begins with assumptions, the possibility of using a theoretical lens, and research problems that ask about the meaning attached to individuals or groups in social problems. Apart from that, this data analysis technique is carried out interactively through this data analysis process data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing.

Moreover, the researcher conducts the data analysis by first summarizing the results of interviews and observations related to the catcalling phenomenon experienced by women in Makassar and the signs used in these activities. Then, the researcher presents the data in charts and narrative texts and concludes.

In data reduction, the researcher selects and simplifies the data to provide convenience when concluding the study's final results. Then, all research results from the field that have been collected are selected again to determine which data is appropriate to use. Because the data obtained from the field is large, complex and complicated. Furthermore, the researcher reduced the data in this research by conducting interviews and observation. Then, the interview results regarding the catcalling phenomenon and the signs used in the activity will be recorded and then selected and simplified to make it easier to conclude it.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Findings

The findings describe the data analysis of the refusal strategy of catcalling by women in Makassar analyzed from the view of Ferdinand Saussure. Catcalling as sexual harassment is done in public spaces by giving funny words to the prey. Catcalling as a sign consists of several aspects, such as oral signs and non-oral signs. The semiotic analysis of catcalling is a sign built on a signifier and signified in an object, concept, and linguistic symbol that forms a sign (meaning). The signifier is the significant element that interprets the object verbally and nonverbally. In addition, the signified is the significant element that gives concept and meaning to the interpreted object.

Catcalling is a phenomenon that is familiar to adults and even teenagers. Not only in Makassar, catcalling also occurs in various countries around the world. Many women feel proud when they become victims of catcalling because they consider it as a sign that they are attractive in the eyes of others. In Makassar, catcalling is not a compliment, but a form of sexual harassment perpetrated by others. Based on the data obtained, catcalling is done in various ways, such as whistling when the perpetrator sees the victim's body and calling out in a teasing tone or making sexual comments to others in public places such as sidewalks, markets, terminals, cafes, and campuses.

In addition, this research was conducted at various universities or campuses in Makassar, with the object of research being active students as victims who experienced catcalling. Researcher also finds seven universities or campuses in Makassar where

catcalling occurred. Catcalling information is obtained from the researcher's relatives who studied at the seven universities. So that researcher takes data or interview research participants (RP) to be analyzed based on semiotic analysis. Therefore, the total data obtained was twenty-seven women research participants (WRP). The details of the data are as follows:

Chart 1. the Number of Women Research Participants

The pie chart above shows catcalling often occurs in Makassar because this act is the beginning of committing sexual violence. Unsurprisingly, some of the viral sexual harassment information on social media, such as Tiktok, Instagram, Facebook, and WhatsApp, comes from Makassar. This effect is because there is no action and a lack of understanding of semiotics by victims in dealing with catcalling. Therefore, the researcher reviews this research to analysis the types, causes, and strategies for refusal so that victims and readers of this research can recognize catcalling verbal and nonverbal signs to be equipped with knowledge in dealing with catcalling in the future.

Furthermore, a sign cannot be conveyed or captured utterly independent of the signifier; the signifier or signified is a sign itself and also a linguistic factor. Therefore, there are seven refusal strategies, each finding can be explained as follows.

A. Ignoring to Perpetrator

Ignoring the perpetrator by not calling is the right strategy for victims to deal with catcalling. The data evidence from observations and interviews is as follows:

Data 1: WRP 014

“Tidak untuk merespon, karena jika kita merespon ke pelaku catcalling maka pelaku akan merasa diberikan panggung untuk melakukan tindakan tersebut”.

“Not to respond, because if we respond to the perpetrator of catcalling then the perpetrator will feel given a platform to commit the act.”

In data 1, it is assumed that WRP 014 tried not to respond to the perpetrator when she was a victim of catcalling; she reasoned that if she responded to the perpetrator of catcalling, then the perpetrator would feel given a platform to commit the act. The signifier for not doing something to the perpetrator is the word not to respond. The signified is the concept or meaning of the word itself that the victim feels afraid, anxious, or worried if the perpetrator commits a dangerous act, so she does not respond to the perpetrator. Furthermore, in data 2, the ignoring strategy is also listed as follows:

Data 2: WRP 027

“Sejujurnya, saya hanya mengabaikan mereka. Bagi saya itu adalah strategi terbaik yang bisa saya lakukan”.

“Honestly, I just ignore them. For me, that's the best strategy I can do”.

In Data 2, several sets of words become signifier and signified. The signifier is ignore. Apart from that, ignore is also a verb form whose signified word is a form of rejection of the opposite sex. Based on the results of observations and interviews, WRP 027 experienced catcalling on the sidewalk, and she just ignored it because she felt disgusted by the actions of the perpetrator.

B. Viralizing Cases on Social Media

Viralizing catcalling cases on social media such as Instagram, WhatsApp, TikTok, and Facebook is one of the perpetrators' strategies in dealing with catcalling when the victim is harassed by the perpetrator, which we can interpret as a movement to reveal someone's sensitive information. The end of the actions taken by social media users is usually in the form of insults and diatribes for the perpetrator. When a case is virtualized and gains comprehensive engagement, the case has been successfully raised. And it is not uncommon for those who spread the perpetrator's identity and people who also empathize with feeling satisfaction because the perpetrator has been considered to receive instant punishment in the form of netizens' insults. The data that has been collected is as follows:

Data 3: WRP 003

“Menyuarakan pada media sosial, jika pelaku ingin melakukan catcalling saya akan membuatnya viral dan jera terhadap perbuatannya”.

“Voicing on social media, if the perpetrator wants to do catcalling I will make it viral and deter him from his actions”.

In data 3, there is a sentence that has a signifier and signified, and the signifier is voicing on social media. The series of words contribute to the element it accompanies. The meaning it gives depends, of course, on the elements that precede and follow it, namely, voicing on social media. Voicing is a gerund of the root word voice which gives a meaning relation in action. Then on is a preposition that requires an adverb, namely social media. The adverb on social media has a meaning relation that refers to digital technology that has the potential to make everyone connect and interact from various messages.

Therefore, the results of the meaning relationship create a signified as concept of the signifier, which means spreading catcalling cases on social media so that all netizens can see the depraved actions carried out by the perpetrator so that the perpetrator has a deterrent effect on the actions he took against the victim.

C. Fighting to the Perpetrator

In interacting with other people, It is not uncommon for us to face unpleasant things, one of which is catcalling. To prevent catcalling, we need to be able to divide ourselves or be equipped with the knowledge of dividing ourselves so that the victim can protect herself independently, as done by the research participant as follows:

Data 4: WRP 025

“Melawan jika pelaku sudah berlebihan”.

“Fight back if the perpetrator has gone too far”.

In data 4, there is a sentence that has a signifier and signified, while the signifier is fight back. Fight is a verb while back is an adverb, so verb + adverb = verb phrase. Moreover fight back is also a bound morpheme in the derivational morpheme category, Bound morpheme is a morpheme that cannot stand alone and can only appear in combination. Bound morpheme always appears the root (root) and sometimes combined with other morphemes. Derivational morpheme is a morpheme that, when bound to other morphemes, form a new morpheme/word or to form a word with a different lexeme from the previous word. Then fight back is derived from the word fight (verb) and also as a root that gets an additional morpheme back (adverb) which turns the word verb into a verb phrase, therefore, it is why morpheme back is a derivation morpheme because it turns the word verb lexeme into a verb phrase lexeme. So fight back has the meaning of fighting back which is categorized as signified because the victim gives an attack as done by the perpetrator so that the word back is added to fight back.

D. Reporting to the Police

Reporting to the police is also a form of resistance to catcalling if the victim feels excessive harassment by the perpetrator. The data that can be analyzed are as follows:

Data 5: WRP 009

"Melaporkan kepada pihak yang berwajib"

"Reporting to the authorities"

In data 5, there is a series of words in the form of reporting to the authorities as a signifier. Reporting is a gerund of the word report (verb). A Gerund is a verb (verb) that changes its function to a noun (noun); the way to change it is to add -ing at the end of the word. Besides that, the gerund in reporting functions as a subject because it is located at the beginning of the sentence. Then the authorities is a noun that functions as an object. Authorities mean people have power and actions, such as police, prosecutors, lawyers, presidents, and judges. So the meaning of the word authorities referred to in the sentence above is a police officer who acts to overcome or provide a deterrent to the perpetrator. Therefore, the signified of reporting to the authorities is giving a complaint to a police officer to take action against the perpetrator of catcalling.

E. Leaving Places Prone to Catcalling

Leaving places prone to catcalling is also as refusal strategies of catcalling usually the victim leaves the area to find a crowded place to be comfortable in doing activities, as explained in the data below:

Data 6: WRP 018

"Menghindar dengan cepat dari tempat itu."

"Dodge quickly away from the place."

In data 6, there is a sentence that has a signifier and signified, while the signifier in the series of words above is dodge quickly away. Dodge has meanings such as avoid, run, and fend off, meaning that someone avoids unwanted things. Then the word quickly away is an adverb which means fast and lightning. When verb + adverb = verb phrase which functions as subject because it is located at the beginning of the sentence. So the signified in dodge quickly away is the victim avoids the perpetrator of catcalling quickly therefore, she feels comfortable and no longer gets catcalling harassment.

F. Pretending to Call Family

Pretending to call family is part of the strategy of rejecting catcalling carried out by the perpetrator; when the victim feels anxious, worried, or afraid of the perpetrator's treatment, the victim can take a cell phone to pretend to call family. The data of this research can be analyzed as follows:

Data 7: WRP 012

"Jika saya berada didalam lingkungan catcalling seperti di tempat umum dll. Saya akan berusaha menghindari dengan berpura pura menelpon agar pelaku menganggap ada orang yang menemani saya sehingga tidak akan merayu saya. Kalau perlu saya membawa teman cewek dan cowok agar saya bisa aman".

"If I am in a catcalling environment such as in a public place etc. I will try to avoid it by pretending to call so that the perpetrator thinks there is someone accompanying me so that he will not seduce me. If necessary, I bring a girl friend and a boy friend so that I can be safe".

In data 7, WRP 012 is pretending to call her family to avoid being catcalled. Pretending is derived from the word pretend (verb). Pretending is a gerund (noun) because the suffix -ing is added, then to call is the infinitive of the word call, so the series of letters is the signifier. Pretending to call has a meaning or concept that describes a victim pretending to call her friend or family to get protection from the perpetrator of catcalling, so that concept is called signified.

G. Reprimanding with Sound Loudly

Giving a reprimanding in a loud voice can also be used as a strategy in refusing to catcall so that the perpetrator feels afraid of the yelling from the victim so as not to be considered weak. The data that supports this section are as follows:

Data 8: WRP 013

"Saya menegur dengan suara lantang agar pelaku tidak berani merayu dan menyentuh saya".

"I reprimanded in a loud voice so that the perpetrator does not dare to seduce and touch me".

In data 7, WRP 013 performs a catcalling refusal strategy by reprimanding her in a loud voice so that she can protect herself. Reprimanded in a loud is the signifier that provides information to reprimand in a loud voice. At the same time, the signified is the concept or meaning expressed by the victim in order not to disturb herself by catcalling. A sign can only be understood if the

relationship between these two sign components is connected to the meaning or concept. So the signifier and signified in reprimanded in a loud are interconnected by morphology, syntax, grammar, and phonology to create meaning.

DISCUSSION

Experiencing catcalling requires having a strong mentality in order to resist the act strongly. All women can certainly anticipate catcalling. It is just the courage to refuse that makes women still hesitate. Many people understand that catcalling is just a joke or compliment to a woman. However, jokes and compliments can reek of harassment if the woman or victim objects or get angry at the perpetrator's actions. Therefore, in this section, the researcher explains catcalling rejection strategies so that victims can avoid catcalling in various places such as sidewalks, campuses, cafes, and markets. Catcalling is a form of sexual harassment committed in a public place (Ramadan, 2018).

The researcher also analyzed the victim's strategies in dealing with catcalling rejection using Ferdinand Saussure's signifier and signified theory in semiotics. This concept sees that meaning arises when there is an association or in absentia relationship between 'signified' and 'signifier.' According to Stam et al., (1992), a sign is the union of a signifier with an idea or signified. A signifier with signified is useful. Conversely, a sign cannot be conveyed or captured entirely apart from the signifier; The signifier or signified is the sign itself and the linguistic factor. Based on the data obtained from the results of the analysis, the researcher found a strategy to resist catcalling, among other things Ignoring the Perpetrator, Viralizing Cases on Social Media, Fighting to The Perpetrator, Reporting to the Police, Leave Places Prone to Catcalling, Pretend to Call Family, and Reprimand with Sound Loudly.

Ignoring perpetrator is the act of ignoring the perpetrator by running to a place to get protection. Because humans are expected to maintain individual relationships between fellow human beings, humans will eventually ask for help in dealing with rampant forms of catcalling in the surrounding environment. Self-adjustment to the social environment is the process of individuals adjusting to society, so that individuals can establish a harmonious relationship with their social environment. According to Johnson & Indvik (2001), people always interact with their environment to get protection from catcalling. Adjustment to the social environment of catcalling is the process of individuals adjusting to society to get protection or establish a harmonious relationship with their social environment. Social protection is one of the psychological aspects that need to be developed in individual life, both protecting oneself and others in catcalling.

In data 24, it is assumed that WRP 014 tried not to respond to the perpetrator when she was a victim of catcalling; she reasoned that if she responded to the perpetrator of catcalling, then the perpetrator would feel given a platform to commit the act. The signifier for not doing something to the perpetrator is the word not to respond. The signified is the concept or meaning of the word itself that the victim feels afraid, anxious, or worried if the perpetrator commits a dangerous act, so she does not respond to the perpetrator.

Viralizing Cases on Social Media, on social media, such as Instagram, WhatsApp, TikTok, and Facebook, is one of the perpetrators' strategies in dealing with catcalling when the victim is harassed by the perpetrator, which we can interpret as a movement to reveal someone's sensitive information. The end of the action taken by social media users is usually insults and abuse for the perpetrator. Sawhney et al., (2005) stated a case is virtualized and gains comprehensive engagement. Pennington & Birthisel, (2016) claimed sexual violence must first be publicized on social media in order to get the attention of the public. And it is not uncommon for those who spread the identity of the perpetrator and people who also empathize to feel satisfaction because the perpetrator is considered to have received instant punishment in the form of netizen insults.

This effort to publicize catcalling cases on social media aims to make the relevant parties, whether the perpetrators or institutions that have the right to make policies, immediately take concrete steps to resolve the case. The intention is to publicize cases of catcalling and sexual harassment on social media to get public attention, but if you are not careful, it will actually backfire on the victim. Information and communication technology with all issues in the modern world including social movements (Garrett, 2006; Olorunnisola & Martin, 2013; Soares & Joia, 2015)

Fighting to the Perpetrator is an act of counterattack by the victim to the perpetrator because he feels that his security cannot be disciplined, therefore, the victim fights back against the act of catcalling by the perpetrator. According to Charmaz, (2017), support is important to be able to move together against catcalling. To prevent catcalling, we must be able to divide ourselves or be equipped with knowledge of dividing ourselves so that victims can protect themselves independently.

Reporting to the police is also a form of resistance to catcalling if the victim feels excessively harassed by the perpetrator.

One strategy to inhibit the number of sexual harassment is support from the victim's immediate environment or reporting at the police station in an emergency. When the victim wants to report, it is the environment that supports her. Apart from that, the victim plays an important role in being able to overcome or resolve this sexual harassment case, this requires courage from the victim to report the incident to the police, because in general the victim experiences threats from the perpetrator and this makes the victim feel afraid and traumatized. Fileborn & Vera-Gray, (2017) illustrates catcalling prevention is carried out during the examination process so that victims will get justice for what happened to them. Crime is the name or label given by people to judge certain acts as evil. Therefore, its meaning is very relative, which depends on a person's judgment to judge it. So what one person calls a crime, does not always have to be recognized by other parties as well (Culpeper, 2011).

Leaving places prone to catcalling is also a refusal strategy against catcalling, usually the victim leaves the area to find a crowded place to be comfortable in doing activities. Another strategy that many participants discussed was to ignore catcalls (Cote, 2017).

Pretending to call family is part of the strategy to reject catcalling by the perpetrator; when the victim feels anxious, worried, or afraid of the perpetrator's treatment, the victim can take the cellphone to pretend to call family. Pretending to call has a meaning or concept that describes a victim pretending to call her friend or family to get protection from the perpetrator of catcalling, so that concept is called signified.

Finally, reprimand with sound loudly can also be used as a strategy in rejecting catcalls so that the perpetrator feels afraid of yelling from the victim so that they are not considered weak. In data 31, WRP 013 performs a catcalling rejection strategy by reprimanding her in a loud voice so that she can protect herself. Reprimanded in a loud is the signifier that provides information to reprimand in a loud voice. At the same time, the signified is the concept or meaning expressed by the victim in order not to disturb herself by catcalling.

CONCLUSION

In this section, the research concluded catcalling refusal strategies so that victims can avoid catcalling in various places such as sidewalks, campuses, cafes, and markets. Because many people understand that catcalling is just a joke or compliment to a woman. However, jokes and compliments can reek of harassment if the woman or victim objects or gets angry at the perpetrator's actions.

Therefore, the researcher analyzed the victim's strategy in dealing with catcalling refusal by using Ferdinand Saussure's theory of signifiers and signs in semiotics. This concept sees that meaning arises when there is an association relationship between 'signified' and 'signifier'. Based on the data obtained from the analysis, researcher finds strategies to resist catcalling, including Ignoring the Perpetrator, Viralizing Cases on Social Media, Fighting to The Perpetrator, Reporting to the Police, Leave Places Prone to Catcalling, Pretend to Call Family, and Reprimand with Sound Loudly.

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